

Supplementary Material for “Shortening Feedback Loops in a Live Game Development Environment”

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I. OVERVIEW

This report presents supplementary material to the paper “Shortening Feedback Loops in a Live Game Development Environment” published in the proceedings of VL/HCC 2021. It includes more details on the approach, more detailed accounts on the development of the game prototypes, and a more in-depth discussion of consequences of the design.

II. A LIVE PROGRAMMING ENVIRONMENT FOR GAME DEVELOPMENT

Our approach to enabling a live programming workflow for gameplay code involves two principles. First, we want the game to be running at all times in order to be able to relate changes to the game directly. Rather than finding ways to simulate game-like behavior while inside an edit mode, we believe that inverting the question and trying to find a way to enable efficient editing while inside the game will provide a more general solution to previewing changes.

Second, the programming tools are aware of the continuously running game. As a result, our tools can both leverage the potential of run-time information and deal with challenges that arise from viewing the game while it is live, rather than only in its initial state inside the editor. This also entails, that the view of the running game itself needs to be flexible to accommodate for the deep integration with the programming tools.

In this section, we describe the design of our proof of concept game environment¹. We first outline its architecture, as it informs design decisions on the user interface level, then we describe the environment on a high level. Finally, we describe how we approach the two design principles: keeping the game running and integrating live feedback with the code, the editor, and the game itself.

A. Architecture and ECS

The environment is built around the Entity-Component-System (ECS) architectural pattern. The ECS pattern, and more generally a data-oriented approach to architecture, has been frequently used in games for its versatility for heterogeneous simulations and performance [1], [2]. It separates identity, data, and code explicitly: entities are identifiers that

may contain a set of components; components include all data of the game and act as descriptors of the traits and state of an entity; systems query the game world for all entities that possess a specific combination of components and then read or write the data of those components. Typically, all systems will be executed during each tick of the game. A game world contains the mapping of all entities to their components.

As an example, the entity that represents a game character may have a sprite component that contains a reference to its image file, a movement component that contains its current speed, and a position component with its current position. A render system would then query the world for all entities that have both a position component and a sprite component and then draw each sprite’s image at the respective positions. A physics system would query for entities that have a position component and a movement component and add the entity’s current movement speed to its current position.

The environment is built in Squeak/Smalltalk [3], [4], which allowed us to quickly iterate on the design and provided us with hot code reloading infrastructure. Our environment provides several tools that users can recombine to form workspaces to work on specific aspects of the game. This is similar to most software in this area, for example Unity² or Blender³ contain a number of different tools that can be arranged by the user to support their current task. Our environment is composed of a number of tools (see Figure 1), including tools to define the data layout of components (②), running queries against the game state also enabling the user to edit the results (①), editing the code of systems (⑥), viewing a rendered version of the game (⑨), controlling the active game state snapshot and game time (④), or profiling (⑤).

B. Editing in a Running Game

The first principle we consider for live programming is to keep the game in a running state at all times even when editing the game state. To achieve this, we formalize the idea of state snapshots as a central concept within the game editor. A state snapshot is a copy of all data that the game state is made up of at a given moment in time. The game begins with an initial state snapshot Δ_0 which represents the game state that the developers prepared and will later be shipped as the

¹The source code of the environment is publicly available on GitHub at <https://github.com/hpi-swa-lab/tools-interactive-simulations/>

²<https://unity.com/>

³<https://www.blender.org/>

Fig. 1. A screenshot of our environment. We list the elements that will later be mentioned here for reference: ① entity filter, ② component structure definitions, ③ template definitions, ④ pause/play/step, auto-persist, and replay controls, ⑤ profiling and frame breakdown, ⑥ system code editors, ⑦ a code watch, ⑧ query connection bubbles, ⑨ a game view

game. While running, the game will be in the current state snapshot Δ_i at the time i when users observe the system. The environment provides several controls to advance the game state (④). If a user presses the restart button, the game’s current state Δ_i will be reset to Δ_0 . Further, users have fine-grained control over how the state advances via the step button, that advances the state to Δ_{i+1} . In terms of the ECS pattern, a state snapshot is a deep copy of the state of all components, while the code is the definition of the systems.

When editing in a running game, the challenge is to identify to which snapshot a change to the state should be applied to. Only applying the change to Δ_i would mean that the change is not persisted and the effects only exist temporarily as the game is being played. Typically, such changes to game state are the direct result of the game logic, for example moving the game character left in response to a key press. However, they might also be applied by developers when experimenting with the game. In contrast, changes to Δ_0 are persisted and will exist in future runs of the game. Applying a change to both Δ_i and Δ_0 is straightforward for modifications of state that is constant between snapshots. This is, for example, the case when changing the position of a piece of wall in a game level. As its position is constant, moving it in both states is a consistent change. For non-constant, derived state, however, such as a patrolling enemy’s position, persisting a change becomes ambiguous. If the user moves a patrolling enemy in Δ_i with $i > 0$ and we apply that change to both Δ_i and Δ_0 , the current state Δ_i will likely have become inconsistent, as restarting the game and advancing it to the same point in time i as before will likely result in the enemy being placed

elsewhere, as its starting position is now different.

A similar problem arises with entities or components that do not exist in Δ_0 . This is commonly the case for entities that spawn during gameplay, such as particles or projectiles, as well as for procedurally generated levels. For these, we encounter a situation where a change can only be applied in Δ_i , as the correct place to persist a change would not be in the game’s initial state, but rather in the entity’s production rules embedded in the system code.

For the first problem, where developers change derived state that also exists in the initial state Δ_0 we offer the user to explicitly opt-in to a persisting mode. By activating a checkbox, any change to an entity or component that exists in both Δ_0 and Δ_i will be applied to both state snapshots. The user can toggle this behavior by holding a modifier just before doing a change, enabling a quick workflow of experimentation and persisting changes. The editor’s user interface color changes subtly to show what mode the user is currently in and will also change color in response to holding just the modifier to ensure that the user is aware of the current mode.

While more sophisticated solutions are possible [5], we approach the second problem, where an entity or component does not exist in our persisted state Δ_0 , by showing the user clearly where changes to data can be persisted, and where a change would only occur in Δ_i , by coloring any fields where persisting is not possible in a shade of red. As such, users are still free to experiment with any values but are also made aware of the temporary nature of their changes.

To support persistent changes to entities that are spawned at runtime, we added “entity templates”. A template (③)

Fig. 2. Applying a persisted change in the editor while the game is in the current, observed state Δ_i , will apply the same change to state Δ_0 , and Δ_r , if a replay snapshot currently exists.

(1)	Δ_0 200	Δ_n 200	Δ_{n+1} 50	Δ_i 50
			value decreases by 150	
(2a)	Δ_0 300			Δ_{i+1} 300
				do persisted change to 300
(2b)	Δ_0 300	$\Delta_{r=n}$ 300	Δ_{n+1} 150	Δ_{i+1} 150
			value decreases by 150	

Fig. 3. In (1), the game starts with a state Δ_0 of 200. At point in time n , the value is still at 200, but decreases by 150 at $n+1$. As such, the value will then be at 50 at the current point in time i . If the user wants to persist a change to the value setting it to 300, the current value will also be at 300 in (2a). This is inconsistent, as the decrease by 150 is no longer considered. In (2b), we create a replay snapshot Δ_r at point in time n before the value decreases. Since we can now replay from Δ_r , $\Delta_i + 1$ will arrive at a consistent value.

contains a definition of an entity with its components and can be spawned at runtime by copying the components to a new entity. Next to the defined components, it will also copy a special “InstanceOfTemplate” component that marks it as having been instantiated from its template. When the user changes a value in the template’s definition, we can use this marker component to find all entities that have been spawned from this template and apply the same change to these entities in the Δ_i state. This concept faces similar issues as described in our first problem: changing for example the starting health points of an enemy template would reset the health points of all enemies to the newly set value, rather than considering damage an entity may have already taken. But at the same time it allows for consistent edits in Δ_i to entities that did not exist in Δ_0 .

Tweaking both derived and constant values during the game is a frequent process when it comes to balancing the game to reach a certain level of difficulty. To support this process, we allow users to save a snapshot Δ_r of the current game state Δ_i and use it as a point of replay (4). To enable replay, users can start recording from time r . During the recording, all external events to the game, such as pressing keys, moving the mouse, or manually spawning an entity via the editor, will be recorded. When the user starts the replay, Δ_i is reset to Δ_r and as the game time advances, we trigger all recorded external events. Changes that are done while in persisting mode will then be

Fig. 4. We filter for the OnebitPosition component in the entity filter, as such it is considered a source for the OnebitPosition component. The systems on the right that receive a red line query for the OnebitPosition component within their code. The yellow bubbles traveling along the lines visualize past queries for each tick, the larger the bubble, the larger the query result’s size.

applied to all three states Δ_i , Δ_r , and Δ_0 , while non-persisted changes will only be applied to Δ_i .

Users can let the editor automatically replay the recording to get continuous feedback on their changes. For example, users can modify the system code to tweak a one-off interaction, such as entering a trigger zone and see how the recorded situation evolves given this new system code. Further, they could also modify template definitions to change values such as jump height or speed and see the effect of that change play out without manually redoing the jump. While the repeated execution of the recording makes feedback available quickly, it may result in inconsistent game state as changes to the code are directly reflected in the game behavior, rather than from Δ_0 or Δ_r .

To specifically support continuous and consistent feedback on code that triggers an effect once, such as procedural level generation or trigger zones, users can configure the editor to auto-restart. When active, the game will reset to Δ_r if it exists, or Δ_0 otherwise, after each save of system code or persisted change to data values of components or templates. This allows keeping changes to derived information consistent, as changes are re-applied from a consistent state of the game and time is correctly advanced to reach a new derived state that incorporates the changes.

C. Integrating with the Editor

The second aspect we consider essential for a live programming experience with a game development environment is a tight integration of the running game with the tools for editing the game and the tools for editing code. In our prototype, the code is directly integrated within the game development environment in the form of ECS systems that appear in a separate panel (6).

The editor also visualizes some of the underlying semantics directly. The arrangement of ECS systems editors (6) corre-

sponds to the execution order of the ECS systems. Users can change their order via drag and drop. Similarly, dataflow can be visualized by filtering for usage of a specific component. Systems that use the selected component will be colored to allow for faster navigation. Further, users can enable drawing connections from panels (⑧), which act as source of specific components, to the code systems that use them (see figure 4). For example, using the entity filter tool (①) to search for entities that have a Transform component and then enabling the connections, will draw a line to all systems that query for Transform components. While the game is running, bubbles sized to the number of entities that matched each query will travel along the connections. This helps users to both find usages of components, as well as usage patterns: performing certain actions in the game, such as spawning particles, will likely cause a high increase in bubble sizes for certain components.

In the system code editors, to better understand the relevant code, users can place inline watches on any expression (⑦). Once marked with a watch, the values running through the game will be streamed into the editor. This is in contrast to the typical debugging workflow, where the game or program will be halted to inspect values. Users can configure different ways to display the values, for example plotting numbers, displaying not just the most recent, but the last five values at the same time, or visualizing results of draw commands.

The entity filter tool (①) is well suited to quickly create ad-hoc editors for various use cases. Similar to an ECS system, it will run a query against the game’s world and return all matching components. The data inside the query tool is fully editable and always refers to the current state of the game, as all values are updated synchronously after the game step. To ensure that editing is still convenient, even when the values change continuously, such as the acceleration of a falling body subjected to gravity, we freeze the value when an edit interaction is started (see figure 5). The current in-game value that keeps updating is then shown next to the editing field and gets reset to the newly entered value when the user confirms the change.

Another important aspect of live programming workflows is fast error recovery. Our environment inherits some useful properties from the Squeak/Smalltalk environment in this regard: any error will open a debugger where code can be edited, and execution can be restarted and proceeded. Alternatively, if the error is immediately obvious to users, they can just continue editing in the editor and upon the next save the environment will resume execution. Errors in drawing code will be isolated and, again, after saving or clicking the then disabled drawing surface, execution will be tried again.

D. Integrating with the Game

Finally, to foster aspects of direct manipulation and reduce the distance between the tools and the game, the environment supports users in integrating custom tooling directly within their game code. The working hypothesis is that the line between tooling and game needs to blur to allow writing tools

Fig. 5. The coins value is currently being edited, but increases with each game tick. We display this actual value next to the input field while the user is editing and freeze updates to the input field.

within the domain of the game with as little of cognitive overhead as possible. As such, while users could change all relevant values through the entity filter by mutating values directly, they can instead use an existing tool system or write their own system to accommodate a certain use case more adequately.

For example, creating the typical gizmo user interface element used in most engines for changing an object’s transformation will happen through the use of a custom system. This system will likely be inserted after the main rendering system to draw on top of the game’s entities and wait for mouse events to either select an object or start transforming it accordingly.

To ensure that users can keep an overview, we allow grouping systems into sets and toggling them in their entirety. Users may thus define one set of systems to be used as the core game, and another, either replacing this set or running in addition to it, to support different editing use cases. We can compare this to the model of aspect oriented programming [6], where tooling systems can be inserted before or after gameplay systems to either preprocess or visualize the same data that the gameplay systems are working with. In this way, game code can be cleanly separated from tool code, as the tooling code can be isolated into a separate system before or after the game code. Message passing or enriching information can also be realized within this framework: systems earlier in the pipeline can spawn entities that carry events or information meant for later consumption by tool systems. Alternatively, they can attach tool components to existing entities, meaning we do not enter a situation where a game object class needs to be composed of both game-related and tooling-only properties, rather we can isolate tooling properties into dedicated tool components.

Further, we allow users to open multiple views (⑨) on the game and configure which systems run to render that view. This allows users to realize various common tools, such as the typical four-split view in 3d game editors, where one view displays the perspective view on the game and the other three are locked to the x, y, and z-axes respectively.

Fig. 6. Two separate views are opened (A, B). For each view, there is an AnnoCamera component shown in the entity filter. Only the second camera (B) has its generatedWorld attribute set to true (D), thus the first camera (A) will not be considered during culling. As such, it allows inspecting the result of the culling algorithm. Further, a drawing debug system for the isometric tiles is active and shows the coordinates of the tilemap.

III. DISCUSSION

In this section, we describe our experience of working with the proposed environment while developing three prototypical games. Further, we discuss how our solutions to realize the two principles to provide faster iteration cycles worked out in practice.

We implemented three simple games of different genres: an “Anno 1602”-like isometric map renderer to benchmark the drawing debug capabilities of the environment and its rendering performance, a top-down tower defense game on a 2D grid, and a real-time side-scrolling platformer.

The map renderer involved infinite random map generation and culling (see Figure 6). With the help of debug draw systems, it was easier to understand how isometric tiles need to overlap. By opening multiple view tools (see A and B in Figure 6) and attaching different cameras to them, we were also able to debug the tile culling mechanism while staying within the game’s code (9). To do so, we added a flag whether the camera was to be considered as a main camera and only

Fig. 7. Demonstration of the pathfinding debug overlay. This optional system will draw the next steps of each enemy actor as blue circles and draw a number over each tile with a movement cost of more than zero, such as the greyish boulders that have a movement cost of four.

drew tiles that were within the view of a main camera (the generateWorld property in Figure 6 (D)). All views that were not marked to contain a main camera would then show the culled view as the main camera was moved away.

The tower defense game explores complex interactions between various types of actors: towers can receive upgrades for projectiles for different effects, terrain elements can be placed by the player and need to be taken into account by the pathfinding of walking and flying enemies, a user interface supports buying upgrades and placing towers. The game makes heavy use of templates (3). Towers and enemies were balanced by tweaking the global template definitions and automatically replaying a scenario (4) where enemies should still be able to reach the base. A custom debug drawing overlay was used to debug the A* pathfinding implementation (see figure 7). By toggling the system when incorrect pathing behavior occurred, pausing the game, placing watches in the algorithm’s implementation, and then stepping forward in ticks using the time controls (4), we could investigate how the implementation worked, both in terms of values flowing through the algorithm and through visualizing the chosen path and the fields’ traversal costs on top of the game.

The platformer game demonstrates the use of a simple physics system. Live values are changing constantly as actors are subjected to gravity and other forces. Again, the replay feature (4) was of help by recording a section of gameplay. For example, doing a jump of maximum distance, then replaying that jump, pausing, and placing level tiles accordingly. Additionally, the framework allowed us to implement a level builder directly within the game using ECS systems. When the user presses the button to instantiate or move an entity, we attach a “PendingPlacement” component to this entity. We then add a system to our game that queries entities with the “PendingPlacement” component and move these to the

cursor position. When a mouse click occurs, we remove the component from entity, thus leaving it at its new position.

As outlined while discussing the game prototypes, the user interface supported us in various ways to quickly assemble tooling for domain-specific debugging and testing. Especially the ability to define custom sets of systems to run in a view and to be able to quickly toggle systems proved helpful for a variety of use cases. The custom views encouraged a mindset of creating small systems for game-specific purposes that made the development and debugging workflow easier. Sharing these tool systems between games, however, was rarely straightforward during our testing. Typically, the data layout of components was slightly different, or a different projection for cameras was in use, necessitating a different calculation to resolve mouse coordinates. To enable sharing systems across games, we experimented with adding parameters to systems that each game can tweak, as a form of higher-order systems. For example, systems that needs to resolve camera coordinates, could take a projection method as a parameter. In this way, the systems that work with camera coordinates can be reused in games that have different camera projections.

Beyond this initial account of how the environment can provide short feedback loops, it remains to be investigated how well the presented methods scale, as all games had very small scope. However, at least for exploratory purposes, we believe that the environment enabled us to find suitable, working designs faster than in traditional game engines. For this, too, a quantitative analysis could be performed. Similarly, the scope of changes was defined to be very small. To enable larger changes such as refactorings to be applied to the game as well, while maintaining live programming benefits, a concept such as edit transactions [7] may be worth exploring in the context of ECS and games.

A. Performance Considerations

The overall performance of the system was acceptable for the types of games we tested on. Most significantly, the rendering of the Squeak/Smalltalk system took up considerable resources, especially for the map generator game. Since only software-based rendering through blitting operations is currently available in Squeak, this was an expected limitation and we have experimented with an OpenGL based renderer that was indeed able to push performance further.

We did, however, have to make some compromises to keep performance high: in particular, the entity filter is optimized to update as quickly as possible, as a query could even match all entities that currently exist in the game if filtered by a position component. To maintain good performance, we do not currently address multiple changes to one data point within the same tick. For example, an entity that is added and then removed within the same frame will currently not appear in queries at all, as the UI updates only after the tick has finished processing.

This case did come up during our prototyping, for example for collision events, which were added by the physics system as entities early during the tick, so later systems could read

them, and a final cleanup system removed them again before the next tick would start. As such, it was not possible to debug what collision events occurred, as the cleanup system had already removed all event entities when the tool UI had updated. While the current system works without any overhead, as the state is taken as-is after each tick, a more accurate implementation would need to keep track of the modifications done in each tick.

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